

EFFECT OF EMBEDDED OPTICAL FIBERS ON THE STRUCTURAL INTEGRITY OF COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY : An frequently expressed concern about composites with embedded optical fibers is the potential for an embedded optical fiber to act as a crack initiator, leading to untimely failure of the structure. An added concern is optical fibers close to regions of inherent stress concentrations, arising from to macroscopic or ply-level geometric features. The present study is concerned with determining if the introduction of embedded optical fibers into regions of stress concentrations is critical by further reducing the static structural integrity. Two cases, i.e. composites with ply-drops and bolted joints, were investigated with embedded optical fibers in critical locations. It was found that embedded optical fibers did not significantly affect the integrity of the composites with ply-drops or bolted joints. The inherent stress concentrations associated with such features completely dominate any disturbance caused by single optical fibers.

KEYWORDS: smart structures, embedded sensors, optical fibers, structural integrity, failure mechanisms, aerospace applications.

INTRODUCTION

Embedded optical fiber sensors is a promising way to reliably monitor composite aircraft structures in real time. However, issues of fiber placement, and how properties of the composite are affected by the presence of the fiber and fiber sensor under a given set of parameters, have not fully been investigated. It may in many cases be required that an optical fiber is placed in, from a structural integrity point-of-view, seemingly unfavorable locations, to satisfy sensing requirements and other constraints, such as available ingress/egress points and geometry. An embedded optical fiber, having a diameter an order of magnitude larger than the reinforcing fibers of a composite, constitutes a disturbance in the microstructure giving rise to stress concentrations. It has been demonstrated that the optimal position of an optical fiber in a composite is in the direction of surrounding co-linear plies, where the fiber is most protected and causes least disturbance to the microstructure [1-3]. Studies have shown that placing optical fibers in other directions may in some cases lead to a decrease in strength, in particular in compression [4, 5]. However, small diameter optical fibers, i.e. 125 μm or less, did not appear to influence strength or damage development in any way. Even fiber loops, where the fiber changes direction and disturbs the microstructure considerably, does not lead to

premature failures [6]. The optical fibers in the latter case did, however, effect the damage evolution by being preferred sites for matrix cracking (ply splitting).

Ply drop-offs are used to decrease or increase the stiffness or strength locally while avoiding joints and hinges, keeping the structural weight down. This is achieved by dropping (or adding) a number of internal plies, thus changing the thickness of the laminate (Figure 1). Such design details are common in aircraft wings and stabilizers, and in helicopter rotors. Analytical investigations of the interlaminar stresses and delamination growth in composites with ply drop-offs have shown that interlaminar shear and normal stresses arise within the tapered region under applied loads, promoting the initiation of cracks [7-9]. It has been found that the compressive and tensile strengths of a tapered laminate is generally less than that of its thin section [7]. The bending-extension coupling caused by the eccentricity of the mid-planes of the thin and thick sections, contributed strongly to interlaminar normal and shear stress development. Under tensile loading, the maximum interlaminar stresses occur near the point indicated by A in Figure 1, where the belt joins the core at the beginning of the thin section. Based on experimental studies, the failure mode was either matrix cracking followed by delamination of the adjacent interfaces or delamination between the belt and the core, depending on the material and the directions of the plies in the taper region [8].

Bolted joints are used extensively in aircraft structures to attach composite panels to the underlying structure, allowing removal for servicing. The stress concentrations induced by the hole along with the localized loading lower the load-carrying ability of the joint. A number of failure modes are possible, including net-section (tension) failure, bearing failure, shear-out, or bolt failure (Figure 2). Many investigators have studied the failure of composite bolted joints loaded in tension/compression; for a comprehensive review see Ref. 12. Much of the work has been devoted to studying the effect of various parameters on the failure mode, such as the thickness and ply directions and the relative ratios of geometric quantities. Delaminations around the hole are commonly seen before ultimate failure, and may actually relieve stresses near the hole raising the strength of the joint. Besides the geometric factors, material properties (fiber, matrix, and interface), fastener type and associated parameters (size, clamping force, washer size, and tolerance), and joint design (type, loading, etc.) all affect the joint strength.

Many aircraft composite structures contain features which introduce stress concentrations into the structure. It is important that the embedded optical fibers do not lead to any degradation of the structural integrity of the composite in combination with other inherent stress concentrators. The present study is an experimental investigation of the effect of optical fiber placed in regions of stress concentrations in a composite. Two configurations are studied, optical fibers combined with ply-drops, and optical fibers near loaded holes in bolted joints.

Figure 1. Schematic of tapered laminate.

Figure 2. Bolted joint failure modes. a) bearing failure, b) net section failure, c) shear failure, and d) bolt failure.

Figure 3. Lay-up of tapered laminate with embedded optical fibers. Dark areas indicate resin pockets.

Figure 4. Drawing of the bolted joint specimen indicating the locations of the optical fibers in either of two configurations, i.e. with 0 or 90 degree optical fibers.

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

Materials and Specimen Design

Laminates were fabricated using Ciba-Geigy Fiberdux 6376/HTA epoxy/carbon-fiber prepreg, using the manufacturer's recommended curing schedule. A 30-ply laminate, $[\pm 45/90_2/0_2/OF/0_2/\pm 45/0_4/90]_s$, was studied, where 'OF' indicates the location of the optical fibers. In both the tapered and the bolted joint specimens, optical fibers parallel (0 degrees) and perpendicular (90 degrees) to the loading direction were investigated. Optical fibers were of silica glass, being of 125 μm nominal diameter and having a 5-10 μm polyimide coating. The laminate thickness was approximately 4.1 mm.

In the tapered laminate four 0 degree plies were dropped from the laminate to yield the 26-ply lay-up of the thin section, $[\pm 45/90_2/0/OF/0/\pm 45/0_4/90]_s$. The thickness of the thin section was approximately 3.5 mm. Owing to lay-up on a flat plate, the symmetry planes of the thick and thin sections did not coincide, resulting in a configuration as shown in Figure 3. The plies were dropped with an interval of 2.5 mm. Two optical fibers were embedded in each specimen. In the 90 degree case the optical fibers were placed in front of the resin pockets where the thin section begins. This was determined to be the likely failure site based on analysis and experiments [7-9]. The specimens with the optical fibers placed in the 0 degree direction had the optical fiber between the two dropped plies, in the center of the specimen, as indicated in Figure 3. Specimens were nominally 11 mm wide and 175 mm long.

The bolted joint specimens had the same lay-up and had the optical fibers embedded between the same plies as the thick section of the tapered specimen. Four optical fibers were placed in each specimen, either in the 0 or in the 90 degree direction, positioned as illustrated in Figure 4. Two holes, each 6 mm in diameter, were drilled into each specimen using steel drill bits, as indicated in Figure 4. The distance, d , between the hole edge and the optical fibers was chosen to be 2 mm.

Specimen Conditioning

Both Room Temperature (RT) and High Temperature wet (HT) conditions were investigated. The as-fabricated specimens contained approximately 0.1% moisture. In the RT case, specimens were dried out at 120°C and kept in a desiccator until tested at ambient conditions. In the HT case, the specimens were kept in an environmental chamber at 70°C and 95% relative humidity and tested at this condition. The tapered HT specimens were conditioned for approximately 6 months, while the bolted-joint HT specimens were conditioned for over a year before testing, after which the moisture content was approximately 1.1%.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Tapered Laminates

Strain gages were fitted to some specimens in three locations, one on each side of the specimen in the thick section, and one on the lower side of the thin section. Other specimens were not strain-gaged; in these cases only load was monitored. A spacer was used in the grip on the thin side of the specimen to center the specimen on the symmetry axis of the thick section. Fixed, hydraulic wedge-type grips were used, and testing was performed quasi-statically in tension or compression in a hydraulic test machine under displacement control until failure. In the compressive case, plates were clamped around the specimen outside the gage section to avoid buckling.

Figure 5. Bolted assembly.

Figure 6. Test configuration of bolted joint with anti-bending fixture. Specimen and steel tabs were free to move axially.

Bolted Joints

Experiments on the bolted-joint specimens were carried out in a servo-hydraulic test machine in tension. Load was transferred to the specimen via steel tabs, which were bolted onto the specimen using 6 mm diameter titanium bolts, as shown in Figure 5. A washer was used between the head of the bolt and the composite, and the bolts were torqued to 9 Nm. To reduce bending effects, a steel fixture was clamped around the specimen and steel tabs. Teflon film was placed between the specimen and the fixture to reduce friction so the joint would be able to deform freely in the axial direction within the fixture.

Strain gages were placed on both sides of the specimens in the center between the holes, measuring axial strains. Load was applied quasi-statically in tension in displacement control at a few percent strain/minute until failure.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tapered Laminates

Mechanical Properties

Typical tensile load-strain curves are presented in Figure 7 for both the RT and the HT cases without optical fibers. The non-aligned neutral axes of the thick and thin sections caused by the taper resulted in bending of the specimens. Because of the rigid boundary conditions imposed by the gripping arrangement, the specimen assumed an s-shaped posture. In the thick section this resulted in a decreased strain at the SG1 position (Figure 7), and an increased strain at the SG2 position. In the thin section, the curvature was reversed, with the lowest strain occurring on the side of SG3 and the highest strain on the opposing surface. The strains were seen to be proportional to the load until failure in both the RT and HT cases, with the failure load slightly lower in the HT case.

During compression, the moment imposed on the specimen by the non-aligned neutral axes was reversed (Figure 8). This led to a reversal of the bending shape of the specimen, with SG1 seeing the lowest compressive strains due to the tensile bending component at this location. By coincidence, SG2 and SG3 detected almost identical strains, as the strain at SG2 was lowered further and the strain at SG3 was raised by the bending. As in the tensile case, the numerically largest strains occurred on the surface opposite to SG3. The strains were not linear with load in the compressive case. In compression a significant difference between the failure load in the RT and HT conditions was observed.

Four to eight specimens were tested for each condition. In general, no effects of the embedded optical fibers were detected. The failure loads of the experiments on tapered laminates are summarized in Figure 9 and Table 1, with standard deviations. It may be seen that any effects of the optical fibers on the failure of laminate were statistically insignificant. The much lower strength observed in HT compression relative to RT compression likely was an effect of the deteriorated matrix and interface properties after moisture and heat exposure, reducing the constraint of the carbon fibers which therefore tended to microbuckle at a lower compressive load than in the RT condition.

Figure 7. Tensile load-strain curves of tapered laminates in the RT and HT conditions without optical fibers.

Figure 8. Compressive load-strain curves of tapered laminates in the RT and HT conditions without optical fibers.

Figure 9. Summary of strengths of tapered laminate with and without optical fibers in the RT and HT conditions. Error bars on top indicate standard deviation.

Failure modes

In tension, ultimate failure of the tapered specimens was matrix cracking of the 90 and ± 45 degree plies, and fibrous tensile fracture of the 0 degree plies, interconnected with extensive delaminations. Failure invariably was centered where the thin section met the tapered region, although the failure zone could extend several centimeters to each side.

In compression, the failure also occurred where the thin section met the tapered region. In this case, the failure zone was relatively confined to this location, although delaminations could

Table 1. Average strength of tapered laminates with no, 0° , or 90° embedded optical fibers (OF), in kN/mm* with standard deviations.

	-----Tension-----	
	RT	HT
No OF	3.33±0.07	3.18±0.24
0 deg.	3.27±0.04	3.21±0.24
90 deg.	3.33±0.12	3.14±0.14
	----Compression----	
	RT	HT
No OF	2.38±0.07	1.61±0.04
0 deg.	2.37±0.11	1.64±0.02
90 deg.	2.44±0.14	1.70±0.07

*Strength given by failure load/specimen width.

extend in both directions. Microbuckling of both the 0 and ± 45 degree plies appeared to have occurred considering the confined nature of the fracture zone. Unfortunately, post-failure crushing excluded further analyses.

In one specimen with 90 degree embedded optical fibers, tested in compression in the RT condition, the test was stopped before microbuckling failure took place. This specimen was studied further using optical microscopy to determine the extent of the accumulated damage, and whether the optical fiber played a part at this stage of the failure process. Part of the area where the thin section meets the taper is seen in Figure 10 (specifically the lower part of the specimen between SG2 and SG3, referring to Figure 8). Delamination cracks may clearly be seen on both sides of the dropped plies and through the location of the optical fiber. This is consistent with the aforementioned results of other investigators. That the delamination passes close to the optical fiber, and in the case shown in Figure 10 through the optical fiber-composite interface, was not unexpected, since the optical fiber was purposely placed in the most critical location. In Figure 11 is shown the same area but from the other side of the specimen. In this case the delamination did not pass through the optical fiber interface but traveled in another plane. There was thus no evidence to suggest that the optical fiber participated actively in the failure process.

Bolted Joints

Mechanical Properties

Owing to the load-line asymmetry, some bending was detected in the bolted joint experiments despite the constraint exercised by the steel fixture clamped around the joint. Depending on the clamping force of the supporting fixture, the strain behavior was slightly different, as seen in Figure 12. In this figure, Spec. 1 had the higher clamping force, and exhibited a higher failure load and a reversal of bending owing to the larger constraint of the support. Clearly, the loading on the specimen was complex, but as the objective of the present study was a comparison between specimens with and without embedded optical fibers, the exact loading was not critical as long as it was repeatable. The high clamping force of Spec 1 was used throughout the experiments.

Figure 10. Interlaminar cracks in tapered region of specimen tested in compression in the RT condition.

Figure 11. Same region as seen in Figure 10 but from the opposing edge.

Failure was in all cases catastrophic, with the load dropping instantly upon failure. Four specimens were tested for each case. Typical load-strain curves for the various cases tested are shown in Figure 13, using the average strains from strain gages on both sides of the specimens. No significant differences in the loading behavior was seen between specimens having no optical fibers or specimens containing embedded optical fibers, or between the RT and HT cases. Load was linear proportional to strain until failure in all experiments.

The failure loads are summarized in Figure 14 and Table 2. No significant differences in the failure loads were seen between specimens with or without optical fibers. A small but significant difference was observed between specimens tested in the RT and HT conditions, respectively.

Figure 12. Strains measured on surfaces (front and back) of two specimens showing typical strain response.

Figure 13. Load-average strain curves of bolted joint tested in various conditions and with various optical fiber (OF) configurations.

Figure 14. Failure load for shear-out of bolted joints in the RT and HT conditions with and without optical fibers (OF). Error bars on top indicate standard deviation.

Table 2. Average load carrying capability of bolted joints with no, 0°, or 90° embedded optical fibers (OF), in kN, with standard deviations.

	RT	HT
No OF	21.4±0.9	20.2±0.7
0 deg.	21.4±0.9	19.8±0.5
90 deg.	21.1±0.7	19.8±0.3

Net section failure of outer 45 deg plies

Net section failure of 90 deg plies

Figure 15. Schematic of failure mode of bolted joint.

Failure modes

All specimens tested exhibited identical failure appearances, which may be characterized as predominantly shear-out, see Figure 15. This was true regardless of the environmental condition or optical fiber configuration. Looking at the ply-level failure, a predominance of matrix-dominated failure modes was evident. The 90 degree plies generally failed at net section with delaminations at interfaces above and below which enabled the sliding of the 90 degree plies during the shear-out process. Furthermore, the outer 45 degree plies failed by bearing failure combined with net section failure along the 45 degree direction of the outer ply. The bolts also showed clear evidence of shear deformation in all cases. The 0 degree plies all failed in shear from the edges of the hole. No damage was associated with the embedded optical fibers.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the experimental data and the fractographic investigation, the following conclusions may be reached:

1. Having embedded optical fibers passing through or parallel to ply-drops in a laminate does not have any significant effects on the static strength of the laminate. This is valid even for optical fibers placed in the most critical locations as determined by analysis.
2. The placement of optical fibers in composites very close (2 mm) to bolted joint holes does not affect the damage development or failure modes of the joint, and therefore not its load carrying capability, when subjected to quasi-static loading.
3. Embedded optical fibers in conjunction with geometrical complexities such as tapers and bolted joints does not appear to cause problems for common aircraft laminate lay-ups. The inherent stress concentrations associated with such features completely dominate any disturbance caused by single optical fibers.

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